

Cheap and FAIR: Building a Serverless Research Data Repository

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Abstract—In this tutorial we will walk our attendees through the process of starting from data files in a folder, organizing them into a Globus collection and then publish a data catalog website to GitHub pages using the "Serverless Research Data Repository" (SRDR) tools.

At each stage of the process we will highlight the features required to make a published dataset compliant to the FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse) principles.

The tutorial is targeted both at gateway developers interested in deploying and administering their own data portal and at attendees interested in publishing their data in the most effective way.

Index Terms—Science Gateways, FAIR, Globus, GitHub, Markdown

I. TUTORIAL SPECIFICATIONS

TABLE I
TUTORIAL LENGTH, LEVEL, AND REQUIREMENTS

Tutorial Length	3 hours
Recommended Skill Level	Intermediate
Prerequisites	Familiarity with GitHub and Markdown
Technical Requirements	A web browser and either SSH or a terminal with <code>git</code> and Python. GitHub and Globus accounts are needed (both are free).

II. SERVERLESS RESEARCH DATA REPOSITORY MODEL

The Serverless Research Data Repository (SRDR) architecture was created to meet four goals common to the CMB-S4 Collaboration¹ and other research projects:

- establishing data repositories which incorporate best practices;
- reducing or eliminating operational costs for projects to maintain a data repository;
- providing new projects with a base of good data practices;
- streamlining the later publication or curation of datasets.

While there are several related terms used to describe a data repository, including archive, data portal, and registry, the SRDR is based on this definition:

¹<https://cmb-s4.org>

A data repository is a set of *datasets* organized in and accessible from a *collection*, described by and discoverable in a *catalog*, and managed by one or more *policies*.

These four components provide a conceptual framework for research projects to organize their data practices. We also make the premise that the *quality* of a data repository is based on the policies it adopts (e.g., metadata standards and availability) and how well it implements them.

III. SRDR ARCHITECTURE

The SRDR architecture, shown in Figure II, is based on the goals, definition, and premise delineated in the previous section. The SRDR combines Globus Guest Collections [1] for data storage and access (the collection) and GitHub [2] Pages for data discovery and description (the catalog) with policy recommendations as a data repository template requiring minimal effort to adopt and operate. Like the Django Globus Portal Framework [3] the SRDR architecture is derived from the Modern Research Data Portal [4] design pattern which provides a robust system of decoupled components. Many projects can deploy a data repository based on the SRDR without incurring any ongoing operational costs. An inspiration for this design is X-ray Tomography Data Bank, or TomoBank [5], which uses Read the Docs to publish a catalog of datasets originally hosted on Petrel at the Argonne Leadership Computing Facility [6].

The SRDR model has been deployed by the authors to build the Data Portal for the CMB-S4 experiment in the field of Cosmology to share maps of the Universe in the microwave regime both within the scientific collaboration and publicly: data.cmb-s4.org. Fig. VII-A shows a screenshot of the CMB-S4 data portal homepage and a page containing list of files identified by their own metadata and containing links to download the actual files via HTTPS through Globus.

IV. TUTORIAL GOALS

The two main goals of the tutorials are to teach the attendees the most important aspects of the FAIR principles and apply them in practice by deploying their own data portal using the SRDR tools.

Fig. 1. Overview of the SRDR architecture.

The tutorial will cover many general aspects of data repositories, also from the users' perspective. Therefore, it is not only targeted to gateway developers but also to scientists who want to learn how to publish their own datasets in the most effective way.

After this tutorials, attendees will:

- understand the basic components of a research data repository;
- understand the FAIR data guidelines;
- know the difference between a dataset's files, metadata, identifier, and landing page;
- the role of machine-readable metadata in data discovery;
- be able to apply access control policies to datasets and their metadata;
- know how to use the tools provided by SRDR.

V. PREREQUISITES

Prior to the tutorial, attendees should have a GitHub (github.com) and Globus (globus.org) accounts. Attendees can reuse their accounts. When creating a Globus account, users can select GitHub to login, so creating a GitHub account first is recommended.

Attendees will have the option to download the sample datasets and run the required scripts on their own laptops. However, it is recommended to connect via SSH to the AWS EC2 instances provided during the tutorial. This will ensure a consistent environment for all attendees.

We will provide pre-configured Globus Guest Collections and GitHub repositories with GitHub Pages enabled.

VI. TUTORIAL AGENDA

TABLE II
TUTORIAL AGENDA

Time	Topic
0:00 - 0:15	Introduction & Setup
0:15 - 0:30	Background: The SRDR Model & Components
0:30 - 0:45	Prepare Datasets
0:45 - 1:00	Background: FAIR Data
1:00 - 1:30	Create the Collection
1:30 - 2:00	Break
2:00 - 2:15	Background: Identifiers & Landing Pages
2:15 - 2:45	Create the Catalog
2:45 - 3:00	Enhancing the Catalog
3:00 - 3:15	Demos: Extending the SRDR
3:15 - 3:30	Discussion & Wrapup

VII. TUTORIAL CONTENT

A. Introduction on SRDR

In the first part of the tutorial we will present the SRDR architecture, as shown in Figure II, we will focus on the role played by Globus (data hosting and permissions) and by GitHub (website hosting and metadata catalog).

We will highlight how the SRDR model is designed to be cheap both in terms of operational costs and in terms of maintenance effort. This is achieved by relying on institutional data storage and Globus services, generally free for academic users, and on GitHub Pages for hosting the static catalog website.

Fig. 2. Screenshot of the CMB-S4 Data Portal, the *catalog* component of SRDR, and a list of datasets.

B. The Datasets and Collection

We will provide example datasets with an open license that the attendees will work with. They will start by packaging the datasets adhering to FAIR principles, including defining an identifier and generating metadata for each dataset. The attendees will ingest the datasets into a Globus Guest Collection that will be shareable through the Globus platform. The attendees will also learn how to configure the Globus Guest Collection with permissions suitable to their needs and to expose the data for HTTPS access. Finally, they will run a tool to extract minimal metadata about the files that will be shared both via Globus and via the Data Portal to enable automated data retrieval.

C. The Catalog

Next the attendees will learn how to use SRDR tools to automatically create Markdown files to build the data catalog as a statically generated website. We will introduce concepts of FAIR related to the catalog and establish nomenclature of its main components. The attendees will then push their Markdown files to GitHub to be automatically compiled by a GitHub Action into a website using Jekyll [7] and published via GitHub Pages. They will be able to navigate through the data catalog on their browser and verify they can download data files directly to their laptop with no need of having Globus installed. Finally we will go through a quick demo on how to build more advanced features on top of SRDR, for example doing visualization and basic analysis right in their browsers.

VIII. INSTRUCTORS

Andrea Zonca is the lead of the Scientific Computing Applications Group at the San Diego Supercomputer Center (SDSC), he has a background in Cosmology and is a member of CMB-S4. He is in charge of maintaining the Data Portal for the CMB-S4 collaboration.

Rick Wagner is the Chief Technology Officer (CTO) at SDSC. Previously, Rick was the Globus Professional Services Manager where he led the development of several data portals and architected the Django Globus Portal Framework. He has supported FAIR data within astrophysics, climate science, and bioinformatics.

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